

INVESTIGATION OF TEXTILE COMPOSITE MATERIALS USING MOIRÉ INTERFEROMETRY

Peter G. Ifju and Brian C. Kilday
Department of Aerospace Engineering, Mechanics and Engineering Science
University of Florida, Gainesville, FL, USA

ABSTRACT

Moiré interferometry was used to investigate the deformation characteristics of braided graphite epoxy textile composite materials. The objective of this study was to characterize the amount of nonuniformity in strain on the surface of specimens for various loading conditions. This information was then used as a guide in the development of standard test methods for such materials. Various loading conditions were tested, including; uniform tension, shear, and thermal expansion. It was found that for all of the loading conditions that strain variations were present on the surface of the specimens. The magnitude of strain variation was highly dependent on the textile architecture and formed a repeating pattern.

INTRODUCTION

Advanced textile composite materials are currently being evaluated as potential structural materials for aircraft. Textile composites have potentially distinct advantages over laminated composites, including; net-shape fiber preform production, which increases the potential for automation. Additionally, they can be made to incorporate through-the-thickness reinforcement for increased interlaminar stiffness, strength and impact damage reduction. Textile composites can be produced via braiding, weaving, knitting or stitching of yarns made from advanced fibers such as carbon, aramid and glass. The polymer matrix is introduced through resin transfer molding, thin film adhesives or powder coating of the yarns. Fiber reinforcement can be made to form a three dimensional sub-structure to give desired properties in prescribed directions. The geometry of the sub-structure also called the fiber architecture forms a repeating pattern, the smallest of which is called the unit cell. For some architectures the volume of the unit cell can be quite large and the exposed area at the specimen surface can be larger than strain gages used for testing of laminated composite materials. If strain variations exist over the area of the unit cell, significant problems may arise if standard mechanical testing practices used for homogeneous materials are extended to textile composites.

Some of the basic questions that are of paramount importance to the textile composite testing community are; how much variation in strain exists over the unit cell, how much variation exists amongst neighboring unit cells, and how do the variations affect the mechanical property characterization for such materials. Even though laminated composites are not homogeneous on the fiber scale, they are over the bondable resistance strain gage scale. Textile composites, however, are not homogeneous over the strain gage scale since the fiber architecture or substructure is on the same scale as strain gages. Additionally, it was found that using smaller gages led to increased scatter in material property measurements [1]. These finds suggest strain variations on the surface of textile composites, although the magnitudes of these variations could

not be documented. This is because strain gages average the strain over the region they span and hence do not have adequate spatial resolution. This is where a full-field method such as moiré interferometry [2] with high spatial resolution, and strain sensitivity, can play a significant role in the understanding of how much variation occurs on the surface of textile composites. Moiré interferometry is a well established experimental technique currently in its second decade of use. Its sensitivity, spatial resolution and full-field capabilities have provided the basis for a "marriage" between the technique and composite materials studies.

While moiré interferometry is limited to 2-D surface measurements, it can still be very useful in documenting various behaviors in order to guide and give insight to the experimentalist whose goal is to develop standard test methods for textile composites, and other such innovative materials. This paper gives examples of how moiré interferometry was used in the Advanced Composites Technology (ACT) Program. Three material behaviors were investigated using moiré interferometry; in-plane tension, in-plane shear, thermal expansion

MATERIALS TESTED

2-D triaxial braids were tested in the experimental program [3]. The yarns were composed of AS4 graphite fibers and the matrix was Shell 1895. The composite panels were manufactured via resin transfer molding. Figure 1 illustrates the fiber architecture for the materials tested. Panels with significantly different mechanical properties were made by varying the yarn sizes and braider yarn directions. Figure 1 also includes a table of the braid parameters for all of the materials tested.

The 2-D triaxial braids are referred to as 2-D since they are composed of layers with no reinforcement interconnecting adjacent layers. They are triaxial since the yarns are oriented in the plane along three directions: the braiders oriented at $+\alpha$ and $-\alpha$ and the axials oriented at 0° . The braids were of a 2/2 pattern where the braider yarns oriented at $+\alpha$ continuously pass over two $-\alpha$ yarns and then under two $-\alpha$ yarns.

MOIRÉ INTERFEROMETRY

Moiré interferometry is an optical experimental technique. It is characterized by high in-plane displacement sensitivity, full-field capabilities, high spatial resolution and high signal to noise ratio. The method involves replicating a very high frequency (1200 lines per mm) crossed-line diffraction grating on the surface of the test specimen. The grating is thin, typically about 0.025 mm, and deforms freely with the specimen. A laser based moiré interferometer, illustrated in Fig. 2, was then used to interrogate the deformed moiré grating. The resulting output is a fringe pattern that represents the displacements on the specimen surface. Since a crossed-line grating is used, both the displacements in the x direction (U-field), and the displacements in the y direction (V-field) can be obtained. The displacement sensitivity of the technique is determined by the frequency of the specimen grating. In these studies a standard sensitivity of $0.417 \mu\text{m}$ per fringe order was used. From the two displacement fields, the normal strains ϵ_x and ϵ_y , and the shear strain γ_{xy} , can be evaluated. In general, the strain is proportional to the frequency of the fringe pattern. For instance the normal strain ϵ_y is calculated by determining the y spacing of the fringes in the V-field pattern, then multiplying by a constant of proportionality which is dependent on the grating frequency used. Simplistically, areas of dense fringes generally correspond to areas of high strain.

TENSION TESTING

A series of tensile tests were performed on all of the 2-D braids. Moiré interferometry was used to determine the displacement fields on the surface of specimens loaded in both the axial and

transverse directions. All of the specimens were 38.1 mm wide and nominally 3.175 mm thick with the moiré fringe patterns taken in the middle of the specimens. The moiré patterns represent the full width (38.1 mm) and a height of 33.0 mm. The specimens were loaded in a 10,000 lb. capacity screw driven testing machine.

For comparative purposes, a tensile test was performed on a unidirectional laminated composite specimen to illustrate the amount of nonuniform behavior of the textile materials. The AS4/3501-6 laminated composite was loaded along the fiber direction. Figure 3 shows the displacements in the loading direction (V-field), and the displacements in the orthogonal direction (U-field). The V-field pattern contains evenly spaced horizontal fringes, where the points on any fringe have been displaced vertically with respect to the points on a neighboring fringe. The displacement field represents uniform tension. Since the spacing of the fringes is constant throughout the fringe pattern, the strains are also constant or uniform. The U-field fringe pattern illustrates the horizontal displacements. The pattern shows that there is uniform Poisson contraction. Again, the deformation is constant throughout. By contrast, the deformation fields on the surface of the textile architectures are much more nonuniform.

Each of the four 2-D triaxial braids were tested in both axial and transverse tension. All of them displayed serious strain variations associated with the textile architecture. Since space is limited for this text only the displacement fields for one architecture (LLL) will be presented for the transverse loading case. Figure 4 Shows the horizontal (U-field) and vertical (V-field) fringe patterns. It is immediately apparent that the fringe patterns differ from those from the laminated material.

The Vertical displacement field shows a cyclic variation of strains along the length of the specimen. This variation corresponds to high normal strain zones followed, in series, by low normal strain zones. Lower strains correspond to the cross-over regions of the braid while the higher strains correspond to the zones in between the cross-over regions. The displacement behavior breached the confines of the unit cell dimensions and formed a global material response. In Fig. 5 a portion of the fringe pattern corresponding to two unit cells, side-by-side, has been enlarged and the full-field strain contours have been superimposed. The strain contours were plotted using the CSAM program developed by the IBM Corporation. From the contour plots shown, the cyclic strain variation is evident. The highest normal and shear strains were always present over the resin rich areas between the braider yarns. This was the case for all of the architectures tested for both axial and transverse loading.

Upon further loading of the specimen, cracking initiated in the resin rich zones where the strain levels were highest. The specimens were loaded well past the load level where first cracking was observed.

The moiré interferometry study provided insight into the behavior of the textile materials. From the amount of nonuniformity of strain in the fringe patterns, it is evident that using small strain gages would produce more scatter in measured average stiffness. The variation of strain is highly dependent on the architectural parameters. To establish a rule of thumb for an optimum strain gage size is therefore not precise. It is the authors opinion that "bigger is better", strictly from a coverage stand point. Larger gages are more expensive, though, therefore a balance should be drawn. It is also the authors opinion that the strain gage should be large enough to span the largest dimension of the unit cell, and include at least three whole unit cells.

SHEAR TESTING

A series of moiré interferometry experiments was performed on textile architectures to validate a new shear test methodology. The methodology includes two advances, a new shear test specimen called the "compact shear specimen", and a special strain gage called the "shear gage" [4-8]. Figure 6 illustrates the specimen, loading fixtures and shear gage. The shear gage is designed to span the entire test section of the specimen, thus integrating or averaging the shear strains. In theory, the shear modulus measurements are not affected by the strain distribution in

the test section. This is the case for global strain distributions on the specimen scale, and local distributions on the preform architecture scale. When gages are placed on both faces of the specimen, any imperfection in loading was corrected for by taking an average.

Moiré interferometry was used to investigate the shear deformation characteristics of the textile specimens. A brief review of the results will be discussed here in order to add validity to the current test methodology.

Three moiré fringe patterns of displacement over the compact specimen test section are shown in Fig. 7. All three patterns are horizontal displacement fields. The first pattern is for a cross-ply laminate, the second is for the SLL braid, and the third is for a weave. The first pattern contains basically horizontal fringes where all the points along one fringe have been displaced horizontally with respect to points along a neighboring fringe, thus signifying shear deformation. The shear strain is related to the fringe spacing in the vertical direction. The fringe spacing changes gradually over the entire test section revealing a smooth strain distribution. By contrast, the fringe spacings for the two textile architectures vary significantly. Here the displacement fields contain repeating patterns that correspond to the cyclic architecture of the textile preforms.

The shear strain distributions are influenced at two scales; the specimen scale, and the micro-mechanical scale of the material. For laminates, the two scales are quite different where the test section of the specimen is 19 mm. and the fiber diameter is on the scale of around 10 μm . As a result, local strain nonuniformities over the fiber scale do not significantly influence the shear strain distribution across the test section. For textiles, however, the preform unit cell sizes are on nearly the same scale as the test section scale; therefore, nonuniformities over the unit cell significantly influence the strain distributions in the test section. This can be thought of as a local strain distribution caused by the repeating textile architecture superimposed over the global shear distribution of the specimen.

Since the shear strain gage integrates the shear strains across the entire test section, the entire strain distribution is averaged, including that influenced at the local and global scales. If only a small portion of the test section were instrumented, such as with the small gages commonly used on the Iosipescu specimens, neither local nor global distributions would be sufficiently sampled. This is because the gages would be too small to cover at least one repeating unit cell of the textile architecture. Additionally, they could not account for the global shear distribution.

The shear test methodology was used to test six specimens of each of the textile architectures. The coefficient of variation for shear modulus was less than 4% for all of the braid architectures tested.

THERMAL EXPANSION

The thermal expansion of the 2-D triaxial braids was examined using moiré interferometry. The objectives were to determine the coefficient of thermal expansion and the amount of strain variation on the specimen surface. The experimental procedure involved; heating the specimen to an elevated temperature, replicating a uniform crossed-line diffraction grating and allowing the specimen to deform as it cooled to room temperature. The thermally induced deformations could then be calculated with reference to the master grating which was used in the replication.

Replicating the grating on the specimen involved three steps. First, a grating was replicated onto an Ultra Low Expansion (ULE) glass using a master reference grating. This operation was performed at room temperature. Silicone rubber was used for the replication since it could withstand the oven temperatures and would separate easily from the epoxy master grating, and subsequently from the specimen. At this stage the master grating and the ULE grating have the same frequency. The second step in the procedure involved replicating the ULE grating on the specimen material at elevated temperature. The grating was formed with a high temperature cure epoxy using the ULE grating. Various temperatures between room and 120° C were used. Over this temperature range the coefficient of thermal expansion of the ULE is considered negligible,

therefore, the ULE grating frequency would match that of the master reference. After 24 hours the high temperature epoxy was cured and the specimen was removed from the oven. While the specimen was still hot, the ULE grating was separated. The specimen was then left to cool. The final step in the procedure was to analyze the deformed grating. Moiré interferometry patterns were generated using the interferometer tuned to the frequency of the original master grating. The patterns represent the relative deformation of the specimen between the elevated temperature and room temperature.

Figure 8 shows the moiré interferometry patterns along the axial and transverse direction for a SLL specimen. The patterns are for a temperature change ΔT of 84°C . A carrier pattern (uniform fringe gradient) has been added in order to aid in the assessment of the strain information. From the fringe patterns the average CTE for the specimen was extracted in both the axial and transverse directions. Strain variations are apparent by the relative fringe spacings which form a cyclic pattern.

CONCLUSIONS

Moiré interferometry can serve as a valuable tool to provide insight to the test method development of novel material systems, such as textile composites. It can provide information on the strain variations on the surface, which in turn, can guide in the instrumentation process. Moiré interferometry can document damage mechanisms to validate the correct use and application of test methods.

REFERENCES

- [1] Masters, J. E., Ifju, P. G., and Fedro, M. J., "Development of Test Methods for Textile Composites," *Proceedings for the FiberTex Sixth Conference on Advanced Engineering Fibers and Textile Structures for Composites*, NASA CP-3211, Drexel University, Philadelphia, PA, 1992.
- [2] Post, D., Han, B. and Ifju, P. G., "High Sensitivity Moiré, Experimental Analysis for Mechanics and Materials," *Springer-Verlag*, New York, NY, 1994.
- [3] Scardino, F., "An Introduction to Textile Composites and Their Structures," *Textile Structural Composites*, Chou, T. W. and Ko, F. K., editors, *Elsevier Science Publishing Co.*, New York, NY, 1989.
- [4] Ifju P. G., "The Shear Gage: for Reliable Shear Modulus Measurements of Composite Materials," *Exp. Mech.*, vol. 34, no. 4, pp. 369-378, Dec 1994.
- [5] Ifju P. G., and Post, D., "A Special Strain Gage for Shear Testing of Composite Materials," *Proceedings of SEM Spring Conference on Experimental Mechanics*, Milwaukee, Wisconsin, June 1991.
- [6] Ifju, P. G., "Evaluation of a New Electrical Resistance Shear Strain Gage Using Moire Interferometry," *Proceedings of SPIE Conference on Photomechanics*, San Diego, California, August 1991.
- [7] "Strain Gages for Shear Modulus Testing of Composite Materials," Micro-Measurements Division, Measurements Group, Inc., Supplemental Data Sheet for Strain Gage Catalogue.
- [8] Ifju, P. and Post, D., "A Compact Double Notched Specimen for In-Plane Shear Testing", *Proceedings of SEM Spring Conference on Experimental Mechanics*, Boston, Massachusetts, May 1989

Fig. 1 Description of the 2-D triaxial braids that were tested in the experimental program.

Fig. 2 Schematic diagram that describes the principles of moiré interferometry.

Fig. 3 Moiré interferometry fringe patterns for a laminated composite material loaded in uniform tension.

Fig. 4 Moiré interferometry fringe patterns for a 2-D braid load in transverse tension.

Fig. 5 Strain contour plots for a small portion of the 2-D braid pictured in Fig. 4.

Fig. 6 The shear test methodology that was used to test the 2-D braids.

Fig. 7 Moiré interferometry fringe patterns for laminated, braided and woven compact shear specimens.

Horizontal displacements (U-field)

Vertical displacements (V-field)

Fig. 8 Moiré interferometry fringe patterns representing thermal displacements.